

Synthetic and Spectroscopic Studies on 5-Carboxymethylthio-2-Arylamino-1,3,4-Thiadiazoles

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Twenty-seven new 5-carboxymethylthio-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles have been synthesised by refluxing 5-mercapto-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole sodium salts with monochloroacetic acid in dimethyl formamide.

THE fact that many thiadiazole derivatives like 5-(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoline-2-thione¹ is an anti-tubercular agent; 2-amino-5-(alkyl-3-oxocyclopentyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole thiosemicarbazone², 2-acetyl-amino-5-sulphamido-1,3,4-thiadiazole³, 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole⁴, 2-ethylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole⁵ and 2-alkylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole⁶ have shown moderate tumour inhibitory properties; 2-amino- Δ^2 -1,3,4-thiadiazolin-5-one⁷ and thiadiazolyl urea⁸ have been reported to be herbicidal and 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole⁹ exhibit remarkable insecticidal properties led the authors to extend this work. We now report the synthesis of 5-carboxymethylthio-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles from several corresponding 5-mercapto-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles, with a view to studying their biological activity.

Results and Discussion

4-Arylthiosemicarbazides required as starting materials were synthesised by the method of Kazakov *et al.*¹⁰, which on being refluxed with carbon disulphide in absolute ethanol gave 2-arylamino-5-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles¹¹⁻¹³.

The 5-carboxymethylthio-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles have been prepared by refluxing 5-mercapto-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole sodium salts with monochloroacetic acid in dimethylformamide¹³.

Spectroscopic Studies

U. V.: The ultraviolet spectra of several 5-carboxymethylthio-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles have been determined using ethanol and methanol as solvents. Absorption maxima of all these compounds have shown the characteristic peaks in the region between 210-420 m μ . It can be seen from the study of the U.V. absorption data that there is a marked bathochromic shift in the absorption bands due to introduction of carboxymethylthio group.

IR: Infrared spectra of several 5-carboxymethylthio-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles have been recorded. Characteristic absorption peaks show the presence of substituted phenyl, -NH₂, -COOH, cyclic C=N, cyclic N=C=S and cyclic C-S groups. The details of infrared absorptions of some compounds are enlisted in Table 1.

Experimental

U. V. spectra were measured in ethanol and methanol solvents. Spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 202 Automatic Recording Spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 720 infrared spectrophotometer and Perkin-Elmer 621 Grating infrared spectrophotometer. Solution spectra were measured in Nujol mulls and KBr disc. The compounds were analysed for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen on

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TABLE I. INFRARED ABSORPTIONS OF SOME 5-CARBOXYMETHYLTHIO-2-ARYLAMINO-1,3,4-THIADIAZOLES

Compound	ν NH	ν CH ₃	Cyclic	Cyclic	Cyclic	ν S	ν COOH	Others
			ν N=C=S	ν C=N	ν N-N=C			
1. 5-Carboxymethyl-thio-2- <i>p</i> -fluoro-phenylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole	3400	2930 1720	1450	1575	1265	1370 760	3220 1720	C-F 1200
2. 5-Carboxymethyl-thio-2- <i>o</i> -hydroxy-phenylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole	3240	2930 2853	1470	1570	1265	1380 750	3200 2925 1625 1380	OH 3240 1380 1180
3. 5-Carboxymethyl-thio-2- <i>o</i> -anisylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole	3225	2925 2853	1470	1565 1495	1260	1380 750	3200 1625 1380 1260	CH ₃ ⁻ 1440
4. 5-Carboxymethyl-thio-2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole	3225	2850	1475	1596 1550	1255	1380 750	3225 1710 1675 1380	C-Cl 820
5. 5-Carboxymethyl-thio-2-(2-nitro-4-chlorophenyl)-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole	3400	2870	1475	1570	1260	1350 750	3230 1265	C-Cl 825 NO ₂ ⁻ 1575 1340

Coleman analyser and data were found well in agreement, within the limits of the possible experimental error, with calculated values. All the melting points were taken by the capillary method and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was tested by thin-layer chromatography.

5-Carboxymethylthio-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles

2-Arylamino-5-mercapto-1, 3, 4-thiadiazoles (0.01 mole) dissolved in sodium hydroxide (0.85g NaOH in 5 ml. water) and dimethyl formamide (10 ml.), was treated with monochloroacetic acid (0.01 mole) in sodium carbonate solution (1.75g Na₂CO₃ in 10 ml. water) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for two hours. It was diluted with water (50 ml.), cooled, filtered and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The resultant precipitate was collected by filtration,

washed well with water, dried and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid to give shining needle-shaped crystals.

Twenty six new 5-carboxymethylthio-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles were synthesised using the above general method. The yields, m.p.s and analytical data of these compounds are described in Table 2.

2-Arylamino-5-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles

A mixture of 4-arylthiosemicarbazides (0.06 mole), carbon disulphide (0.06 mole) and absolute ethanol (25 ml.) was refluxed in a 250 ml. flask on a water-bath at 65-70° for two hours. Excess alcohol was distilled off under reduced pressure and residue after cooling was poured into ice-cold water. The solid which separated was filtered, washed well with water, dried and recrystallised from absolute ethanol.

TABLE 2. 2-ARYLAMINO-5-CARBOXYMETHYLTHIO-1,3,4-THIAZIOLES

S. No.	ARYL GROUP	Molecular formula	Yield %	m. p. °C	ANALYSES		
					%C	%H	%N
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	70	120	Found 44.80 Calc. 44.94	3.24 3.37	15.86 15.73
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	75	130	Found 47.18 Calc. 46.97	3.86 3.91	14.72 14.95
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	65	205	Found 46.82 Calc. 46.97	3.74 3.91	14.81 14.95
4.	<i>p</i> Fluorophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ S ₂ FO ₃	72	130	Found 41.86 Calc. 42.10	2.64 2.81	14.85 14.74
5.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ S ₂ ClO ₃	58	105	Found 39.96 Calc. 39.80	2.78 2.65	13.75 13.93
6.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ S ₂ BrO ₃	72	140	Found 42.32 Calc. 42.10	2.94 2.81	14.86 14.74
7.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	63	165	Found 44.28 Calc. 44.44	3.92 3.70	14.06 14.14
8.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	60	185	Found 44.67 Calc. 44.44	3.84 3.70	14.23 14.14
9.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	68	85	Found 44.52 Calc. 44.44	3.65 3.70	14.27 14.14
10.	<i>o</i> -Phenetyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	60	145	Found 43.94 Calc. 43.77	3.82 3.95	12.91 12.76
11.	<i>m</i> -Phenetyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	70	130	Found 43.62 Calc. 43.77	3.88 3.95	12.76 12.76
12.	<i>p</i> -Phenethyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	72	160	Found 43.73 Calc. 43.77	3.95 3.95	12.62 12.76
13.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	70	150	Found 42.25 Calc. 42.40	3.24 3.18	14.68 14.84
14.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	72	110	Found 42.54 Calc. 42.40	3.06 3.18	14.84 14.84
15.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ S ₂ O ₄	60	62-65	Found 38.41 Calc. 38.46	2.38 2.56	17.82 17.95
16.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂ O ₃	62	152	Found 35.52 Calc. 35.71	2.24 2.08	12.65 12.50
17.	2,5-Dichlorophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂ O ₃	55	42	Found 35.96 Calc. 35.71	2.16 2.08	12.34 12.50
18.	2-Nitro-4-chlorophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ S ₂ ClO ₄	62	110	Found 34.68 Calc. 34.63	2.29 2.02	16.33 16.16
19.	2-Chloro-4-nitrophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ S ₂ ClO ₄	60	115	Found 34.85 Calc. 34.63	2.17 2.02	16.24 16.16
20.	<i>m</i> -Cresolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	55	135	Found 44.28 Calc. 44.44	3.58 3.70	14.32 14.14
21.	1-Naphthyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	70	160	Found 52.81 Calc. 52.99	3.26 3.47	13.51 13.25
22.	2-Naphthyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	69	165	Found 52.86 Calc. 52.99	3.56 3.47	13.42 13.25
23.	2-Thiazolyl	C ₇ H ₆ N ₄ S ₂ O ₃	60	170-172	Found 32.48 Calc. 32.31	2.46 2.31	16.32 16.15
24.	Benzothiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₄ S ₂ O ₃	58	83-85	Found 49.61 Calc. 40.74	2.32 2.47	17.45 17.28
25.	Benzyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	75	168-170	Found 46.86 Calc. 46.97	3.77 3.91	14.76 14.95
26.	Cyclohexyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	72	110	Found 41.34 Calc. 41.52	5.35 5.19	13.38 14.53

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